

Gender STI

D.2.1 - Overview of gender inequalities in STI agreements between EU and third countries

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of WP2 is to perform a deep analysis on gender equality and to define the features that will contribute to identify and remove potential cultural and institutional barriers that hamper the integration of the gender equality actions and policies in international dialogues and cooperation activities in STI. This deliverable presents the results of Task 2.1 and 2.2 that include criteria and indicators to gather insights from key stakeholders through in-depth interviews in order to better integrate the gender equality actions and guidelines in international dialogues and cooperation in STI. The analysis on gender inequalities in STI across Europe and selected third countries will feed the benchmark study on gender equality in STI dialogues.

The information provided in this report discloses the main barriers and success factors that affect the integration of gender equality in dialogues with third countries in the area of STI. The challenges of EU strategy were used to guide the qualitative analysis of D2.1 and have shown that there are different approaches to the gender perspective in international dialogues, projects and international cooperation activities in STI. However, they are not regionally distributed with a clear cut between cultures. Instead, three main level of problems appeared, mostly linked with each challenge of the EU strategy for gender equality deployed by the DG in Research and Innovation: a) Gender equality in careers; b) Gender balance in decision making s; and c) Integration of the gender dimension in R&D content, as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Where each Challenge stems from, according to the interviews

Although the culture of each country seems to appear in many answers, the main finding in the interviews seem to be the institutional profile, and the vision of meritocratic culture embedded in different societies. The implementation of international dialogues and cooperation activities are not able, per se, to change a whole cultural perspective. However, they seem an important instrument of change if cultural differences are considered.

The institutional profile stands by the type of actions deployed by each institution and its professional culture. The former is important to define the range each gender balance action can have in that environment, and the second is more related with the mismatch between inclusion and diversity goals, including gender balance and the idea of meritocracy in STI fields. Finally, data production seems to be one of the main tools able to assess gender balance policies. However, the lack of dedicated personnel to this end is indicated by interviewees.

1. INTRODUCTION

WP2 aims at performing a qualitative analysis on gender equality and to define the features and any other elements that will contribute to identify and remove potential cultural and institutional barriers that hamper the integration of gender equality actions and policies in international dialogues and cooperation in STI. According to the DoA, the specific objectives are:

- Perform a qualitative analysis of the screening and survey findings of WP1 to further understand how gender equality is taken into account and promoted at different levels in bilateral and multilateral STI agreements.
- Gather insights from stakeholders on gender inequalities in STI across Europe and selected third countries.
- Identify barriers and success factors that affect the integration of gender equality in dialogues with third countries in the area of STI.

Deliverable D2.1 provides an overview of gender inequalities in dialogues and the implementation of international cooperation activities and STI agreements between EU and third countries. Based on the results achieved on WP1 through a quantitative mapping, D2.1 was built to give a deeper understanding of the mapping and analysis of gender equality in STI in bilateral and multilateral agreements carried out in WP1. This work aims at creating a wide map that will help researchers, policy makers, and other important actors to better navigate in the multiple dimensions of gender in international dialogues and cooperation activities in the field of STI. To this end, a more balanced gender perspective connected to the objectives of the EU strategy for gender equality has been considered: a) women participation in scientific careers; b) gender balance in decision making; and c) gender equality in R&I content. Specifically, D2.1 presents the results of two tasks:

- T2.1 Criteria and indicators for comparative analysis: The design of the criteria and the indicators to gather insights from stakeholders by establishing features and any other elements that can contribute to removing potential barriers to better integrate gender equality actions and policies in international dialogues and cooperation in STI. The objective is to create indicators and variables for comparative analysis of the gender perspective in bilateral and multilateral implementation activities in STI, considering their preparation, composition, operationalisation, and monitoring phases. The indicators are connected to the objectives of the EU strategy for gender equality: a) women participation in scientific careers; b) gender balance in decision making; and c) gender equality in R&I content, and include gender-related biases, gender attitudes, assumptions, and cultural and institutional barriers, among others.
- T2.2 Insights from stakeholders. Task 2.2 gathered insights from in-depth interviews with key actors identified in T1.1 and other influential decision makers in STI dialogues and actions with third countries. Interviews were performed by the GENDER STI partners across European MS and AC and the selected 10 third countries participating in the project. The goal was to achieve 60-80 interviews

performed by the GENDER STI partners across EU and the selected third countries to ensure balance of perceptions on STI dialogue between EU and third countries. In total, 81 in-depth interviews were carried out in 27 countries. A semi-structured interview guide was used in order to gather insights on the development and implementation of gender equality in international STI dialogues, in particular addressing motives, barriers, drivers and relationships between different issues and factors. Furthermore, the interviews will serve as a starting point to take a deeper dive into the gender equality objectives regarding gender equality in careers, gender balance in decision making and the integration of the gender dimension in R&I content.

D2.1 analyses gender inequality from two perspectives. On the one hand, the first chapter considers the methodological route chosen and developed in terms of coordinating the synchronous and asynchronous work of 18 partners institutions to achieve the qualitative analysis. On the other hand, the second chapter brings the substantive perspective of the in-depth interviews performed with key actors responsible for STI dialogues and international cooperation activities, regarding the gender perspective. Therefore, the focus of the D2.1 is to unfold the results achieved in T2.1 and T2.2, bringing the highlights of the research up to date to the benchmarking analysis (T2.3) which will identify the performance of actors and countries in terms of implementing gender equality in STI.

2. METHODOLOGICAL OVERVIEW

This chapter will describe the methodological design to gather insights from stakeholders through in-depth interviews. It will explore the methodological issues based on novelty brought upon the team by the pandemic restrictions, and the decision to change the in-depth interviews to the semi-structured approach.

2.1 *Adapting to deliver through the pandemic*

D2.1 methodology was adapted due to the mobility restrictions of Covid-19 pandemic. As showed by researchers in works on synchronous and asynchronous learning (Demuyakor, 2020; Fabris et al. 2021; Händel et al., 2021; International Association of Universities, 2020), the need to adapt to online mode challenged the society's digital skills all over the world.

Given the diversity of the consortium that comprises prominent Universities, Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), National Research and Education Networks (NRENs), a funding agency, an NGO specialized in gender in STI, a government institution and companies with high expertise in policy dialogues and international cooperation in STI, it is important to highlight the different juridical nature of the institutions across four continents. Thus, ensuring the interaction between the partners institutions and their interviewees – the key actors in bilateral and multilateral STI dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities – is very important.

To tackle this challenge, the project relied on different management software tools that allowed the synchronous and asynchronous work, taking into account the availability of software through the 18 institutions of the consortium. In this sense, a great amount of the research work was completely reorganised to use *only* online tools, allowing the efficient communication between partners and the organised data collection and preparation for the analysis.

In order to allow efficient and harmonised data collection in Europe and third countries, we adopted a semi-structured approach. In fact, the semi-structured interviews represent the most frequent interview technique in qualitative analyses (Kallio et al., 2016). The semi-structured interviews are qualitative, in-depth, semi open-ended interviews (Duarte, 2005) that aim at investigating different points of view about a fact, through the interviewees' perspective of reality considering the culture and the environment they are embedded in. The semi-structured approach also focuses on guaranteeing the comparability between more than 80 interviews across different institutions, countries, and cultures.

2.2 *The Framework*

A Framework (Table 1) was created to contemplate the assessment of international dialogues and cooperation activities about STI.

The criteria chosen for the framework are the four phases involved in the implementation of international STI cooperation activities, especially, the implementation of international agreements:

- a) preparation of the action,
- b) composition of the action,
- c) operationalisation of the action, and
- d) monitoring of their implementation.

For each criterion, there are indicators composed by one main question and other associated sub-questions. They are organised as such because the main question is formulated in a way that its answer can easily be translated to a quantitative result, as explained below. In total, semi-structure interview guide included 15 questions. Each question received more or less attention depending on the interviewee (to highlight the most appropriate questions and overlook those that do not apply, which shall be a decision of the interviewer).

The indicators were designed to identify gender-related biases, gender attitudes, assumptions, and cultural and institutional barriers, among others, and obeyed the objectives of the EU strategy for gender equality, here defined as Challenges:

- Gender equality in careers (Challenge 1);
- Gender balance in decision making bodies (Challenge 2); and
- Integration of the gender dimension in R&I content (Challenge 3).

Table 1 – Semi-Structured Framework for In-depth Interviews

Indicators	Interview Guide/Questions	Challenge(s)
#1 Preparation of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	1 - Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues in which a significant number of the decision-makers involved were women?	2
	2 - If yes, what kind of dialogue/action was it, how many women were there and were there any incentives for their participation? If not, do you consider that there are limits to women's participation as decision-makers in international dialogues on STI? Which?	1
	3 - In the international cooperation actions you have participated in, has your team/organisation made specific preconditions about the need for the equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action? Were the conditions accepted or not?	1, 2
	4 - Based on your experience, what cultural and institutional barriers could be limiting the inclusion of gender equality measures in international cooperation actions?	1, 2
	5 - In your view, what could be clearly stated in international cooperation dialogues, projects, and	1, 2

Indicators	Interview Guide/Questions	Challenge(s)
	international cooperation activities to foster women's participation in STI actions?	
#2 Composition of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	6 - Do you plan to include gender equality measures in future international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals you might be involved in? What gender equality measures are a priority, in your view?	1, 2
	7 - Do the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the number of women in STI careers in the target countries? If yes, can you provide examples?	1, 2,
	8 - Do the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the gender dimension in research and innovation content (i.e., to overcome the gender gap in research or to generate gendered innovations)? Can you provide examples?	2
#3 Operationalisation of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	9 - During the implementation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you have been involved, do you use and/or produce sex-disaggregated data whenever possible? What kind of data and why is it relevant?	3
	10 - Has the operationalisation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you were involved contributed to gender awareness in the fields of STI? How?	1, 2, 3
	11 - In the implementation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you have been involved, did you/your team provide specific incentives to promote women's involvement in the activities developed?	1, 2, 3
#4 Monitoring of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	12 - Does your team/organisation produce sex-disaggregated data on the results achieved through the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you are/were involved? Which data do you produce?	1, 2, 3
	13 - Does your team/organisation take gender aspects into account in the evaluation and assessment practices in your work in international cooperation? Could you provide examples?	1, 2, 3
	14 - Does your team/organisation implement measures to prevent gender biased research outcomes? Could you provide examples?	3

Indicators	Interview Guide/Questions	Challenge(s)
	15 – Does your team/organization use the outcomes of international cooperation activities to foster gender awareness in the fields of STI? Could you provide examples of ways you have done it?	1, 2, 3

The transcription of data from the interviews was collected into an Excel file, using three different sheets:

- Sheet 1: List of interviewees (Organisation).
- Sheet 2: Long answers which reflect quotes from the interviews.
- Sheet 3: Quantitative results which reflect answers in numerical form.

In the Sheet 1, the partners will include basic information from each of the interviewees. The information collected from each interviewee will allow the team to analyse results not only by country, but also by organisation, by type of role of the interviewees, sector and type of legal entity, if needed. Names of the interviewees were not revealed in the excels to ensure data protection and confidentiality.

In the Sheet 2, the interviewers registered the answers provided by the interviewees. Along the rows, the different indicators (set of questions) are identified as shown in Table 1. The answers, as much as possible, provide specific examples of the work of the interviewee, so that we can draw and analyse specific examples (whether good or bad) with regard to how gender issues are considered within the interviewee’s country, organisation, sector and employment entity.

While Sheet 2 looked into the long answers provided by the interviewees, Sheet 3 was used to translate the results to quantitative figures. The first question in each indicator (with the exception of indicator 4) was formulated in a way that the answer given by the interviewee can be translated as “yes”, “no” or “partially; I don't know; n/a”.

Since the purpose of T2.1 is the development of a framework, using a set of criteria and indicators, to gather insights from stakeholders via individual interviews, this framework was designed complementary to WP1 design which gains insights of gender in STI through document analysis and survey. The WP2 framework allowed an in-depth look into the potential barriers to the observation of gender equality in international dialogues, from the point of view of the interviewees. On the other hand, T2.2 comprises the development of the interviews with the key selected stakeholders. To conduct these interviews, all partners used the common framework which was presented in a handbook introduced to all partners before starting the interviews.

The framework is a tool that, on the one hand, supports the partners in conducting the interviews, and on the other hand allows a comparative analysis of the answers obtained by the different project partners, from different countries and from different groups of stakeholders. The framework is important both to gather qualitative and quantitative insights from the stakeholders. In that sense, it will enable the collection of extensive responses, but it also allows translation to quantitative results that give a quick overview of the status of gender in international dialogues by topic, by country and by group of stakeholders. The quantitative results will be disseminated through GENDER STI channels.

2.3 The Handbook

While the Framework gave the structure, a Handbook was designed to provide practical guidance for the internal GENDER STI team with regards to the development of Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, and this ensuring cohesion between the tasks. The Handbook was developed as internal document to be used exclusively by project partners.

The Handbook was developed for the following purposes:

- To explain the framework built under T2.1 and to be used under T2.2;
- To provide practical guidance on how to use the framework in T2.2; and
- To establish internal reporting procedures regarding the development of interviews in T2.2.

The Handbook was elaborated in the Frequent Asked Questions -FAQ-style, with all the hyperlinks in the index and throughout the document, allowing the partners to click on questions and find the answer. The questions were selected during the Consortium meetings, and especially in the WP1&WP2 regular meetings. The approach of user experience (UX) considered the cultural differences among the partners, and the time zone difficulties. The aim was to ease the access to information, allowing the best results to WP2.

The Handbook had the following structure:

1. How is this handbook structured?
2. What is this handbook for?
3. To which part of the project structure is this handbook associated?
4. What is the purpose of the interviews?
 - 4.1. What are the main results of WP1 Survey?
5. What are the criteria and indicators in the Framework?
 - 5.1. How are the indicators related to the Gender STI Challenges?
6. How to fill in the Framework in the Excel file?
 - a) Sheet 1: List of interviewees
 - b) Sheet 2: Long answers
 - c) Sheet 3: Quantitative results
 - d) Example
7. Who and how many people will be interviewed?
8. What is the profile we are looking for to interview?
 - e) Examples
9. When can the group discuss this?
10. When will the project team conduct the interviews and how will the information be stored? Is it necessary to maintain a record of the interview?

3. HIGHLIGHTS OF IN-DEPTH INTERVIEWS

The distribution of the interviews reflected the distribution of the consortium partners around the globe. It was expected that the consortium partners would use their knowledge and relations to access interviewees. In total, eighty-one interviews were performed around the globe (Table 2), focusing on people occupying important decision-making

positions to negotiating and deciding the content and the strategies of the implementation of bilateral and multinational dialogues, and international cooperation activities on STI.

Table 2 – Geographical Distribution of the Interviews

Continent	Number of interviews
Europe	33
North America	7
Latin America	24
Africa	4
Asia	12
Oceania	1
Total	81

As described above, the indicators were divided into four parts. The aim was to identify if women are involved and gender equality is considered in the different phases of the implementation of the international dialogues and other cooperation activities on STI: preparation, composition, operationalisation, and monitoring. It was designed to achieve engagement with policy makers and stakeholders to clearly understand the different gender perspectives of STI and address the challenges related to the three objectives of the EU strategy for gender equality: gender equality in careers, gender balance in decision making bodies and integration of the gender in R&I content. In addition, the questions were linked with the challenges of EU strategy, with the phases of the actions, and the type of institutions and countries of the interviewees. The objective was to create sets of information able to indicate main spaces of difference, identifying where efficient changes can be made to tackle gender inequalities.

3.1 Preparation and composition of the international actions

The preparation and composition phases are related with the negotiation phase and, because of that, more linked with two dimensions of the EU strategy: gender equality in careers, and gender balance in decision-making bodies. In this session, the main differences appeared between countries, indicating the importance of cultural changes regarding the STI international dialogues, and international cooperation activities, and an expectation alignment.

Most of the respondents answered positively about the significant number of women in the decision-maker positions in preparation and composition of the international actions. Despite the positive result of women participation, some answers indicated interesting highlights by qualifying the conditions under which the number of women was significant.

The first one is that some respondents indicated an increase in the number of women in the last two decades, as Uruguay, Argentina and Panamá. Secondly, some respondents, as in Brazil and Finland, stressed that their answers are positive since their experience are based on areas with the highest rate of women, namely social science and education and culture. In two countries, the answers were balanced between positive and negative: Austria and Brazil. In India, the majority of the answers were negative related to women participation in preparing the international actions. It is also important to highlight that the negative answers were related with hard sciences and strategic fields, and with the highest positions in the decision-making.

Figure 2: Quotes representing answers to women participation in preparation and composition of the international actions (I)

The answers of the second question confirm the tendency identified in the previous ones (Figure 1). Most of the respondents answered that there are no specific incentives or that there are some limits to the participation of women. The only answer indicating concrete incentives is from the USA.

The main content of the answers emphasised the role of countries' and specific regions' culture as incentives or as limitations. This observation includes the acknowledgement of the multiple roles women have in their families and in their societies. It also evidences the mismatch between the society's culture and professional culture.

This mismatch impacts on the international partnerships: some interviewees pointed that the amount of gender balance in international collaboration depend on their partners' vision on the subject, since if the partner has no women in certain positions, there is not much to be done. Also, two factors came up: gender balance measures rely on the political context of each country, and even though there are an increasing number of women in international cooperation work, there are not many female researchers in STI.

Figure 3: Quotes representing answers to women participation in preparation and composition of the international actions (II)

Another important result is that, in many countries, there has been no preconditions about gender perspectives in the negotiation of international dialogues and cooperation activities in the teams of the interviewees. That is, although the interviewees recognise gender inequality as a relevant issue, they do not take active measures to tackle it in their teams.

This discrepancy may be linked with the perception about quotas since it varies a lot. The perceptions reflect at one hand the belief that they are needed and, at the other, their unfitness to the equality purpose in their own team. The discourse supporting the last vision affirms that quotas should not be the reason because women are chosen to take part in teams or to decision making positions.

Another problem raised was the lack of time and human resources to assure those measures, considering the amount of work to be performed, as in Brazil and in Chile: the lack of personnel and time for this task – one example is the high number of scholarships the implementation of gender weights in evaluation process. Finally, it is important to stress that some interviewees in Brazil and in Italy pointed out that, in some fields, quotas would not make any sense because there are very few women in some fields (as in ICT): in these cases, the quotas would be innocuous, and a cultural change is the only path to bring balance.

Issues related to intersectionality were not specifically addressed during the interviews. However, these topics were touched upon in two approaches. In Argentina, Finland and in Canada. Some interviewees stressed the necessity of inclusion beyond the gender perspective. Non-Governmental Organisations, such as *Mujeres en Tecnología* and *DATAGENERO* in Argentina, cover diversity and intersectionality in all their actions by producing gender-disaggregated data. Their training and community activities are exclusive for women and gender dissidences, going beyond binary data to embrace intersectionality.

In Brazil, while addressing the use of gender perspectives in the assessment of scholarships in international collaborations, one of the interviewees stated that if "some women can work and study, it is because it is possible". This seems to indicate the disregard of other different constraints and burdens often much heavier in women. The gender piles up with other barriers to equality – as economic level and ethnicity – interacting and providing complex outputs.

Figure 4: Quotes representing answers to women participation in preparation and composition of the international actions (III)

Therefore, even though the majority of the respondents think that gender equality is an important feature of science, technology and innovation, there are mixed feelings about how to manage and solve the existent unbalance. Most of the interviewees pointed that there is an unbalanced treatment between gender in societies, and that the issue stems from the cultural fabric. However, in spite of some supporters of measures based on quotas, there are decision makers in key positions that think the problem should be addressed in the society, and not in the professional environment. Again, the mismatch seems to appear between knowledge about the social conditions in which women are currently embedded and how to manage their opportunities in professional careers.

Figure 5: Quotes representing answers to women participation in preparation and composition of the international actions (IV)

The answers about whether there is or not a concern with gender in the research content vary substantially among the key actors and countries. Some answered giving a patent negation, recognising the problem. Few interviewees affirm that there is a general goal of gender diversity but not with concrete actions. Some indicated that it only happens when the goal of research is to analyse the gender gap.

A very small number of interviewees affirmed that gender content is important in the international dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities. In this respect, two cases stand out. In Canada, the T-AP EDI Working Group does not have tangible targets, but it does aim to describe and differentiate the keyways in which Equity, Diversity and Inclusiveness (EDI) can be integrated in calls for research (high-level categories). And, in Finland, the gender equality campaign "Invest in Feminist technologies" emphasizing digital tools, e.g., to sustain the economy of small producers, and to prevent violence against women. The interviewee stressed the importance of achievable terminology to the efficient development of the strategy.

3.2 Operationalisation and monitoring of the international actions

The gender balance actions and concerns seem to be less tangible in the phases of operationalisation and monitoring of the international actions on STI, even though there is a fair variation of the answers among the key actors. In this section, questions cover the previous challenges of the EU strategy, however they are more relatable to the integration of the gender in R&I content.

A problem raised in the operationalisation and monitoring of the STI dialogues and cooperation activities is the difficulty to gather and manage data, along with the

discrepancy between what can be decided at a national level and what can be imposed in international those actions.

In some cases, it is possible to identify some variation in answers between the type of institutions. One example is the existence of gender disaggregated data on the results generated by the agreement in terms of generation of teams and programme beneficiaries. Institutions as funding agencies, e.g. the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAPESP) and the National Secretariat of Science, Technology and Innovation of the Republic of Panama (SENACYT), informed that gender disaggregated data is produced in all its funding projects, including those originated in international dialogues and other international cooperation activities. However, more encompassing institutions, as Ministries, tend to not collect or produce gender disaggregated data.

Figure 6: Quotes representing answers to women participation in operationalisation and monitoring of the international actions (I)

Most of the respondents indicated that there is no explicit orientation in monitoring and evaluating these gender aspects on international dialogues and cooperation activities. And, in terms of barriers to these phases, the lack of personnel and time for this task is mentioned - as it was also mentioned in the negotiation session regarding the implementation of gender weights in evaluation process. Regarding the concern with unbiased outcome of research, some interviewees indicated that the problem is taken seriously in the medical field of research.

However, few cases stand out as a good practice. Third countries, especially in Latin America, manage the inclusion of gender-disaggregated data in the research projects they participate, only because it is a European obligation. Many have pointed out that they have learned about gender mainstreaming from international cooperation research projects with Europe. One important example is AECID Costa Rica (Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation): the work with the European Union started the efforts on

gender mainstreaming in all their actions, programmes and projects promoted by Spanish cooperation. According with the interviewee, in terms of development cooperation, the European Union takes this issue very seriously and for the projects they implemented, they received the support of an expert in gender issues to ensure that the gender perspective is included from the formulation of the project, including the indicators.

Another example is the Canadian Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) Partnership Grants affirms that their applicants are expected to embed EDI within the design of the research, as appropriate by using, for example, Gender-based analysis plus (GBA+) and complementary approaches such as anti-racist approaches that consider systemic racism and the intersectionality of different identities in the conceptualization of the research (e.g. age, culture, disability, education, ethnicity, gender expression and gender identity, immigration and newcomer status, Indigenous identity, language, neurodiversity, parental status/responsibility, place of origin , religion, race, sexual orientation, and socio-economic status).

Applicants must consider the topic and people who could be potentially most impacted (positively or negatively) or excluded by the research and proactively seek to include individuals and partner organizations from such groups or communities in the co-development of the research design to ensure a diversity of perspectives and approaches are considered.

Additionally, SSHRC includes diversity considerations in its Research Design module. This is part of SSHRC's commitment to promoting the integration of equity, diversity and inclusion-related considerations in research design and practices. All SSHRC doctoral and postdoctoral award applicants are required to complete this module. Its goal is to encourage them to consider the inclusion of diversity and identity factors in their research proposal, with a view to promote research excellence.

Another point is that, in general, the respondents informed that they do not seek gender awareness as an active goal. Some of the respondents indicated the elaboration of gender awareness programmes in their institutions. Nevertheless, as expected, the institutions and the groups focused on gender perspectives are more tendent to contribute to gender awareness in general.

Figure 7: Quotes representing answers to women participation in operationalisation and monitoring of the international actions (II)

4. CONCLUSIONS

The WP2 aims at performing a deep analysis on gender equality and to define the features that will contribute to identify and remove potential cultural and institutional barriers that hamper the integration of gender equality actions and policies in international dialogues and cooperation activities in STI. The analysis proposes the gathering of insights from stakeholders on gender inequalities in STI across Europe and selected third countries. That information should disclose the main barriers and success factors that affect the integration of gender equality in dialogues with third countries in the area of STI.

In analysing the in-depth interviews with key stakeholders from different approaches, the main path of identification of gender inequalities is in line with EU strategy for gender equality: a) women participation in scientific careers; b) in decision making; and c) gender in R&I content. Two other important division observed in the interviews results are by countries and institutions. There are regressive and progressive cultures in every interviewee mostly given by the institutional culture of each country and respective institutional *loci*, and by the type of the work performed by each institution. At regional level, the influence of European Union framework in international actions was highlighted in some countries. For example, as it was mentioned, in many third countries, especially in Latin America, they manage the inclusion of gender-disaggregated data in the research projects they participate, only because it is a European obligation. Many have pointed out that they have learned about gender mainstreaming from international cooperation research projects with Europe, as a lesson learned along the way.

Regarding the first challenge, meaning the scarce women participation in some scientific careers, seemed much more linked with the cultural fabric of society. The second challenge, related to the unbalanced number of women in decision making positions, seems much more connected with an institutional culture across countries, hampered by narrow understanding of the meritocratic approach. This means that the women and men are judged by the same stakes, even though there is acknowledgement of the difference in women and men's roles in society. The contradictory positions about the use of quotas, for example, is an indicator of this mismatch, which is qualified by the meritocracy discourse. The third challenge seems to be less approached by the institutions.

In the case of agreements, addressing gender in international cooperation is a rather sensitive issue. In bilateral cooperation, agreements are built upon scientific areas of common interest and are mostly gender blind. Having an atomized nature, it is difficult to include such clauses agreement by agreement, project by project. In multilateral cooperation gender issues are not formally addressed, and equality in research teams mainly stem from the inner dynamics of the teams. So, there are no formal parity rules, while in general parity tends to exist, in an organic form. We have guidelines for evaluation panels, for Scientific committees, etc. This is rather a structural matter and asks for more transversal regulatory instruments of stronger value – as Gender Equality Plans, which are eligibility requirements for the Horizon Europe funding. In fact, the recent requirements in ERA funding instruments will have a wide impact on the international cooperation landscape, inducing a broad institutional change and a reverse in cultural bias.

Finally, two main points stand out: the importance of intersectionality and data production. The intersectionality appeared in two main attitudes of the interviewed: how the

unawareness can impact in gender policies, by its full acknowledgement. The data production, on its turn, seem to be one of the main tools able to assess gender balance policies. However, the lack of dedicated personnel to this end it indicated by interviewees.

"To talk about gender is to talk about power and even more when we talk about science and technology. In science and technology we should start, for example, by asking ourselves what gender roles are. We should start with the diagnosis"

Bolivia

Figure 8: Quotes representing answers to women participation in international actions

5. ANNEX 1: THE FRAMEWORK

Indicators	Interview Guide/Questions	Challenge(s)	Country Code
Preparation of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	1 - Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues in which a significant number of the decision-makers involved were women?	2	Answers of interviewees
	2 - If yes, what kind of dialogue/action was it, how many women were there and were there any incentives for their participation? If not, do you consider that there are limits to women's participation as decision-makers in international dialogues on STI? Which?	1	Answers of interviewees
	3 - In the international cooperation actions you have participated in, has your team/organisation made specific preconditions about the need for the equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action? Were the conditions accepted or not?	1, 2	Answers of interviewees
	4 - Based on your experience, what cultural and institutional barriers could be limiting the inclusion of gender equality measures in international cooperation actions?		Answers of interviewees
	5 - In your view, what could be clearly stated in international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities to foster women's participation in STI actions?	1, 2, 3	Answers of interviewees
Composition of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	6 - Do you plan to include gender equality measures in future international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals you might be involved in? What gender equality measures are a priority, in your view?	1, 2	Answers of interviewees

Indicators	Interview Guide/Questions	Challenge(s)	Country Code
	7 - Do the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the number of women in STI careers in the target countries? If yes, can you provide examples?	1, 2, 3	Answers of interviewees
	8 - Do the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the gender dimension in research and innovation content (i.e., to overcome the gender gap in research or to generate gendered innovations)? Can you provide examples?	2	Answers of interviewees
Operationalisation of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	9 - During the implementation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you have been involved, do you use and/or produce sex-disaggregated data whenever possible? What kind of data and why is it relevant?	3	Answers of interviewees
	10 - Has the operationalisation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you were involved contributed to gender awareness in the fields of STI? How?	1, 2, 3	Answers of interviewees
	11 - In the implementation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you have been involved, did you/your team provide specific incentives to promote women's involvement in the activities developed?	1, 2, 3	Answers of interviewees
Monitoring of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities	12 - Does your team/organisation produce sex-disaggregated data on the results achieved through the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you are/were involved? Which data do you produce?	1, 2, 3	Answers of interviewees
	13 - Does your team/organisation take gender aspects into account in the evaluation and assessment practices in your work in international cooperation? Could you provide examples?	1, 2, 3	Answers of interviewees
	14 - Does your team/organisation implement measures to prevent gender biased research outcomes? Could you provide examples?	3	Answers of interviewees

Indicators	Interview Guide/Questions	Challenge(s)	Country Code
	15 – Does your team/organization use the outcomes of international cooperation activities to foster gender awareness in the fields of STI? Could you provide examples of ways you have done it?	1, 2, 3	

6. ANNEX 2: THE HANDBOOK

Gender STI

Comparative analysis framework and interviews handbook – Gender STI, T2.1 and T2.2 (Internal Document)

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How is this handbook structured?

This handbook was structured in FAQ-style. All the hyperlinks in the index and throughout the document are active. **Click on your question and find the answer.**

If you have any other questions, please email the WP2 leaders, USP (gendersti@usp.br).

What is this handbook for?

This handbook provides practical guidance for the internal GENDER STI team with regards to the development of **tasks 2.1 and 2.2, under WP2**. This is an internal document to be used exclusively by project partners, which has the responsibility of verifying the framework and its indicators.

The handbook has been developed for the following purposes:

- To explain the framework built under T2.1 and to be used under T2.2;
- To provide practical guidance on how to use the framework, during T2.2;
- To establish internal reporting procedures regarding the development of T2.2.

To which part of the project structure is this handbook associated?

SPI and USP jointly developed this handbook, as the organisations have different but complementary roles under WP2.

SPI is the partner responsible for T2.1, Criteria and indicators for comparative analysis. USP is the leader of WP2 and the partner responsible T2.2, Insights from stakeholders.

The purpose of T2.1 is the development of a framework, using a set of criteria and indicators, to gather insights from stakeholders via individual interviews. This framework should be complementary to that designed in WP1, allowing an in-depth look into the potential barriers to the observation of gender equality in international dialogues, from the point of view of the interviewees.

T2.2 comprises the development of the interviews with the key selected stakeholders. To conduct these interviews, all partners will use the common framework presented in this handbook.

The framework is to be used by all the project partners conducting interviews with stakeholders. It is a tool that, on the one hand, **supports the partners** in conducting the interviews, and on the other hand allows a **comparative analysis** of the answers obtained by the different project partners, from different countries and from different groups of stakeholders.

The framework is important both to gather qualitative and quantitative insights from the stakeholders. In that sense, it will enable the collection of extensive responses, but also its translation to quantitative results that give a quick overview of the status of gender observation in international dialogues by topic, by country and by group of stakeholders.

What is the purpose of the interviews?

The purpose of the interviews is to enable an in-depth analysis on **how gender equality is observed in bilateral and multilateral cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities**, helping to identify cultural and institutional barriers to the advancement of gender equality in scientific careers, decision-making and R&I content. Hopefully, the interviews will also provide an overview of ways forward, through mention of **good practices and valuable inputs** to improve gender equality in international cooperation dialogues, dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities and actions in its various phases: preparation of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities, composition of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities, operationalisation of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities, and monitoring of its implementation. As so, the questions were organised through these four criteria.

What are the main results of WP1 Survey?

It is highly recommended to read the Survey Report of WP1 ([here](#)¹) before taking these interviews. To be helpful, we copied here three main tables regarding the three main approaches to Gender Equality:

Table 6 of the Survey Report: Side by Side Comparison of Approaches to Improve Gender Equality in Scientific Careers: Europe and Third Countries

Approaches	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Gender equality in recruitment and career progression	74,51%	73.47%	75.47%
Inclusive language for job vacancies	8,33%	14.29%	2.83%
Parental leave policies/flexible work schedule arrangements	35,78%	44.90%	28.3%
Job security for women in the long-term	20,59%	20.41%	20.75%
Visibility to women references in science	31,37%	31.63%	31.13%
Training on equitable hiring practices	13,73%	8.16%	18.87%
Mentorship of women by other women	12,25%	13.27%	11.32%
Incentives for women to lead projects	33,33%	24.49%	41.51%
Gender balanced peer reviews	20,59%	16.33%	24.53%
Retaining women scientists	16,18%	20.41%	12.26%
Unconscious bias training for the scientific community	30,88%	30.61%	31.13%
Other	1,96%	2.04%	1.89%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

Table 7 of the Survey Report: Side by Side Comparison of Issues to Improve the Gender Balance in Decision Making Bodies and Positions: Europe and Third Countries

Issues	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Gender balance in STI policy dialogues	45,10%	41.84%	48.11%
Participation of women in the negotiation of STI agreements	50,49%	46.94%	53.77%
Introducing gender quotas for evaluation panels to ensure a gender-balanced composition	37,75%	37.76%	37.74%
Disseminating updated information, trends and good practices on gender equality in decision-making	32,35%	28.57%	36.79%
Policies to increase the proportion of women in STI	52,94%	52.04%	53.77%
Ensuring transparent nomination and promotion schemes in political and corporate cultures	40,69%	50.00%	32.08%
Unconscious bias training on gender balance in leadership positions	37,75%	40.82%	34.91%
Other	2,45%	2.04%	2.83%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

¹ In the case the hyperlink does not work:

<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1I3PJ7V3kd7RTB79LytIcIsKawzWq3Ak2?usp=sharing>

Table 8 of the Survey Report: Side by Side Comparison of Issues to be Addressed to Integrate the Gender Dimension in Research and Innovation Content: Europe and Third Countries

Issues	Total	Europe	Third Countries
Consider gender in the entire research and innovation process	77,45%	79.59%	75.47%
Address gender bias in research design	41,18%	48.98%	34.91%
Ensure gender balance in evaluation panels	43,14%	35.71%	50.94%
Ensure gender balance in research teams	46,57%	39.8%	52.83%
Include gender factors in application forms	23,53%	28.57%	18.87%
Create criteria to monitor the gender dimension in research content, processes and outcomes	63,73%	63.27%	64.15%
Other	3,43%	4.08%	2.83%
Total	100% (204)	100% (98)	100% (106)

What are the criteria and indicators in the Framework?

The criteria chosen for the framework are the four phases involved in the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities:

- preparation of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities,
- composition of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities,
- operationalisation of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities, and
- monitoring of its implementation.

For each criterion, there are indicators composed by one main question and other associated sub-questions. They are organised as such because the main question is also formulated in a way that its answer can easily be translated to a quantitative result, as will be explained below.

In total, the interviewers will have the opportunity to ask 15 groups of questions, although each of these may receive more or less attention depending on the interviewee selected (to highlight the most appropriate questions and overlook those that do not apply shall be a decision of the interviewer).

CRITERION 1	Preparation of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities
<u>Indicator 1</u>	1 - Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues in which a significant number of the decision-makers involved were women?
<u>Indicator 2</u>	2 - If yes, what kind of dialogue/action was it, how many women were there and were there any incentives for their participation? If not, do you consider that there are limits to women's participation as decision-makers in international dialogues on STI? Which?

<u>Indicator 3</u>	3 - In the international cooperation actions you have participated in, has your team/organisation made specific preconditions about the need for the equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action? Were the conditions accepted or not?
<u>Indicator 4</u>	4 - Based on your experience, what cultural and institutional barriers could be limiting the inclusion of gender equality measures in international cooperation actions?
<u>Indicator 5</u>	5 - In your view, what could be clearly stated in international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities to foster women's participation in STI actions?
CRITERION 2	Composition of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities
<u>Indicator 6</u>	6 - Do you plan to include gender equality measures in future international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals you might be involved in? What gender equality measures are a priority, in your view?
<u>Indicator 7</u>	7 - Do the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the number of women in STI careers in the target countries? If yes, can you provide examples?
<u>Indicator 8</u>	8 - Do the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the gender dimension in research and innovation content (i.e., to overcome the gender gap in research or to generate gendered innovations)? Can you provide examples?
CRITERION 3	Operationalisation of dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities
<u>Indicator 9</u>	9 - During the implementation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you have been involved, do you use and/or produce sex-disaggregated data whenever possible? What kind of data and why is it relevant?
<u>Indicator 10</u>	10 - Has the operationalisation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you were involved contributed to gender awareness in the fields of STI? How?

<u>Indicator 11</u>	11 - In the implementation of the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you have been involved, did you/your team provide specific incentives to promote women's involvement in the activities developed?
CRITERION 4	Monitoring of the dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities
<u>Indicator 12</u>	12 - Does your team/organisation produce sex-disaggregated data on the results achieved through the international cooperation dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities in which you are/were involved? Which data do you produce?
<u>Indicator 13</u>	13 - Does your team/organisation take gender aspects into account in the evaluation and assessment practices in your work in international cooperation? Could you provide examples?
<u>Indicator 14</u>	14 - Does your team/organisation implement measures to prevent gender biased research outcomes? Could you provide examples?
<u>Indicator 15</u>	15 - Does your team/organization use the outcomes of international cooperation activities to foster gender awareness in the fields of STI? Could you provide examples of ways you have done it?

How are the indicators related to the Gender STI Challenges?

The answers provided to the questions in each indicator will allow the WP2 team to collect insights and good practices to overcome the challenges identified in the project proposal:

- Challenge 1: Gender equality in scientific careers at all levels;
- Challenge 2: Gender in decision-making bodies and positions;
- Challenge 3: Gender in research and innovation content.

In that sense, the framework also reflects a tentative match between the relevance of the question and its potential usefulness for each of the three challenges. In the Excel file which will be used to collect the answers, column B identifies the corresponding challenge(s) to each of the indicators.

Questions
Corresponding challenges
Answers

Questions	Challenges	BR1	BR2	BR3
Preparation of the agreements/actions				
1 - Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues in which at least 30% of the decision-makers involved were women? If yes, what kind of dialogue was it, how many women were there and were there any incentives for their participation? If not, do you consider that there are limits to women's participation as decision-makers in international dialogues on STI? Which?	2			
2 - In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, did the teams involved try to understand the percentage of women's participation in STI in the targeted country/region during the preparation of the action? Why or why not?	1			
3 - In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, your team/organisation has made specific preconditions with regards to the need to have equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action? If yes, were these preconditions accepted or not? If not, what is your opinion about implementing quotas for women's participation in international cooperation actions?	1, 2			

How to fill in the Framework in the Excel file?

The data from the interviews will be collected into an Excel file, using three different sheets:

- Sheet 1: List of interviewees (Organisation);
- Sheet 2: Long answers;
- Sheet 3: Quantitative results.

1	A	B	C	D	E	F
2	Questions	Challenge(s)	BR1	BR2	BR3	BR4
3	Preparation of the agreements/actions					
4	1- Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues/actions in which at least 30% of the decision-makers involved were women? If yes, what kind of dialogue/action was it, how many women were there and were there any incentives for their participation? If not, do you consider that there are limits to women's participation as decision-makers in international dialogues on STI? Which?	2				
5	2- In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, did the teams involved try to understand the percentage of women's participation in STI in the targeted country/region, during the preparation of the action? Why or why not?	1				
6	3- In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, your team/organisation has made specific preconditions with regards to the need to have equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action? If yes, were these preconditions accepted or not? If not, what is your opinion about implementing quotas for women's participation in international cooperation actions?	1, 2				
7	4- Based on your experience, what cultural and institutional barriers could be limiting the inclusion of gender equality measures in international cooperation actions? In your view, what could be clearly stated in international cooperation agreements to foster women's participation in STI actions?	1, 2, 3				
8	Composition of the agreements/actions					
9	5- In general terms, do the texts of the international cooperation agreements or project proposals in which you have been involved set intentions to mobilise women in the field of STI? If yes, please provide examples of how those intentions are transposed to the text.	1, 2				
10	6- Do you plan to include gender equality measures in future international cooperation agreements or project proposals you might be involved in? What gender equality measures are a priority, in your view?	1, 2, 3				
11	7- Do the international cooperation agreements or project					

Navigation: List of interviewees | **Long answers** | Quantitative results (+)

Sheet 1: List of interviewees

In this sheet, the partners will include basic information from each of the interviewees (the selected interviewees will have to be agreed with the leader of T2.2, USP).

Code	Her/his role in the organisation	Her/his organisation	Sector (public, private, non-profit)	Type of legal entity
NA1	Research Funding	FAPESP	Public	Foundation
NA2	Member of the Board	UNICAMP	Public	University

To each interviewee is attributed a **code**, which uses the two-letter name abbreviation of the corresponding country (e.g., Brazil – BR) and a sequence number. As shown in the table above, interviewee number 1 from Brazil will use the code BR1, interviewee number 2 will use the code BR2, and so forth. The information collected from each interviewee will allow the team to analyse results not only by country, but also by organisation, by type of role of the interviewees, sector and type of legal entity, if needed.

If the interviewer does not know this information beforehand, she/he should start the interview by asking for the missing information, gaining some knowledge about the person and her/his professional experience.

Sheet 2: Long answers

In this sheet, the interviewers shall register the answers provided by the interviewees. Along the rows, the different indicators (set of questions) are identified, which were presented in

the section above (*What are the criteria and indicators?*). The blue columns (Column C and the following) shall be used to register the individual answers. One column per interviewee, as identified by the code attributed.

Place to fill in individual answers
(one column per interviewee)

Questions	Indicator	BR1	BR2	BR3
Preparation of the agreements/actions				
1 - Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues in which at least 30% of the decision-makers involved were women? If yes, what kind of dialogue was it, how many women were there and were there any incentives for their participation? If not, do you consider that there are limits to women's participation as decision-makers in international dialogues on STI? Which?	2			
2 - In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, did the teams involved try to understand the percentage of women's participation in STI in the targeted country/region during the preparation of the action? Why or why not?	1			
3 - In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, your team/organisation has made specific preconditions with regards to the need to have equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action? If yes, were these preconditions accepted or not? If not, what is your opinion about implementing quotas for women's participation in international cooperation actions?	1,2			

Indicators

All the individual answers shall be registered in **English**. In case the interview is conducted in any other language (which is a possibility, given that interviewer and interviewee will in many cases share a mother tongue other than English), the interviewers shall translate the answers to English.

The answers should, as much as possible, provide specific examples of the working scope of the interviewee, so that the WP2 team can draw and analyse specific examples (whether good or bad) with regards to how gender issues are considered within the interviewee's country, organisation, sector and employment entity.

TIP: the answers should, as much as possible, provide specific examples of the working scope of the interviewee, so that the WP2 team can draw and analyse specific examples (whether good or bad) with regards to how gender issues are considered within the interviewee's country, organisation, sector and employment entity.

Sheet 3: Quantitative results

While sheet 2 looks into the long answers provided by the interviewees, sheet 3 will be used to **translate the results to quantitative figures**. The first question in each indicator (with the exception of indicator 4) was formulated in a way that the answer given by the interviewee can be translated as "yes", "no" or "partially; I don't know; n/a".

This sheet shall be filled in by the interviewer, after the interview. The interviewer shall read the answers that she/he noted down during the interview and simplify each answer to one of the three options:

- Yes = 3;
- Partially; I don't know; n/a = 2;
- No = 1.

Example:

- Question: Have you ever been involved in international cooperation dialogues in which a significant number of the decision-makers involved were women? (...) (Indicator 1)
- Answer from interviewee 1: *I might have. There is one agreement in particular with University X which I remember had a good number of women working on it. I don't know how many, but I remember it caught my attention to see a room full of women rectors, researchers and secretaries signing the agreement. I think around half of the room were women. (...)*
 - **This answer should be quantified with "3", in sheet 3, as it corresponds to "Yes".**
- Answer from interviewee 2: *I have never been in such context.*
 - **This answer should be quantified with "1", in sheet 3, as it corresponds to "No".**
- Answer from interviewee 3: *I have worked both with women and men as decision-makers, but it is hard to remember if there was ever any group with a high number of women. I really can't tell.*
 - **This answer should be quantified with "2", in sheet 3, as it corresponds to "Partially; I don't know; n/a".**

TIP: In case an answer is indeed dubious, the interviewer should opt for 2 ("Partially; I don't know; n/a") or simply leave that space unfilled

The table should be filled in as in the picture below.

According to the answers provided in sheet2 (Long answers), attribute quantitative results to the corresponding questions based on the following classification:
 2 - yes
 1 - partially; I don't know; n/a
 0 - no

		Quantitative results							
		BR1	BR2	BR3	BR4	BR5	BR6	BR7	BR8
PREPARATION	1 - Have you been involved in international cooperation dialogues/actions in which at least 30% of the decision-makers involved were women?	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
	2 - In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, did the teams involved try to understand the percentage of women's participation in STI in the targeted country/region during the preparation of the action?	0	2	0	0	1	0	2	0
	3 - In the international cooperation actions in which you participated, has your team/organisation made specific preconditions with regards to the need to have equal participation of women and men in the preparation and implementation of the action?	1	0	1	2	1	2	0	0
	4 - no corresponding quantitative results for this question								
COMPOSITION	5 - In general terms, do the texts of the international cooperation agreements or project proposals in which you have been involved set intentions to mobilise women in the field of STI?	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0
	6 - Do you plan to include gender equality measures in future international cooperation agreements or project proposals you might be involved in?	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
	7 - Do the international cooperation agreements or project proposals in which you have been involved set targets to increase the number of women in STI careers in the target countries?	2	0	0	2	1	2	0	1

In short, sheet 3 will quantify the answers noted down in sheet 2, allowing a quick comprehensive analysis of the results by the WP2 team, that shall aggregate the results. This analysis will be complementary to the more in-depth examination based on the long answers from sheet 2.

Who and how many people will be interviewed?

In **Europe**, interviews will be conducted with, for example, members of the ERA-related groups on gender and international cooperation, i.e., SWG GRI and SFIC, MS and AC ministries of foreign affairs, gender bodies, funding agencies, and RPOs, among others.

In the **10 selected third countries**, the partners will carry out interviews with key actors in bilateral and multilateral dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities with the EU (e.g., ministries of science and technology, funding bodies for scientific research and leading universities).

To accomplish the task designed, it is expected, **at least, 5 interviews per partner** and the interviews can be carried out online.

TIP: The list of names selected to take part in the survey carried out in WP1 is a good source of possible interviewees to be considered.

What is the profile we are looking for to interview?

We are looking for people occupying decision making positions. Therefore, those who are responsible for negotiating and deciding the content and the strategies of the bilateral and multinational dialogues, projects, and international cooperation activities.

Examples:

- a) Universities: Director of International Cooperation Office; Project Manager
- b) Funding Agencies: Scientific Director
- c) Ministries (Education, Science, Technology, Foreign Affairs etc): Manager of International Cooperation Office.

When can the group discuss this?

To further clarify any issues related with the information gathered during the interviews, we are going to set 2 (two) main focal groups: West and East (as in WP3).

The focal groups will have 1 (one) representative of each institution – preferentially one person involved in the interviews.

The dates and times are to be updated and sent by email/calendar invites.

When will the project team conduct the interviews and how will the information be stored?

It is advised to schedule the interviews **from 25th January to 30th February, since they must be delivered transcribed by 30th March 2022.**

A **Google Drive Folder** was created to each one of the 18 partners, accessible through **this link:**

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1WwWYcrv_3Rpr_9oQr5-7_1-cyxu4pic-

Each partner will be able to see all the folders and its contents, but will only have permission to edit the folder corresponding to the organisation she/he represents.

The main folder will contain:

A) Handbook

B) A document with the latest updates on FAQ, any required adaptations to the procedures, status of the work in progress, dates for upcoming meetings to discuss the work done; etc.

C) Each partner's folder with the latest version of their Excel (permission to edit this folder is only given to the members of the partner organisation and the WP2 leaders).

Is it necessary to maintain a record of the interview?

The interview can be performed by e-mail (written) or on call (spoken). Either way, it is advised to keep the original file.

In case of the interview by call, we advise it to be recorded and the original file stored in the Teams folder of the project.

However, you must deliver the interview transcribed in the excel file – our main source of information.

To do so, we indicate this app to transcribe the information:
<https://support.trint.com/en/articles/3004464-what-languages-does-trint-support>
<https://app.trint.com/plans?interval=month>

Tip: organize yourself to do the transcription for free since the app offers a 7 days free subscription.

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